

The background of the image shows a modern building with a grid of windows and the 'TU Delft' logo on its facade. In the foreground, there are branches of cherry blossoms in full bloom, with pink flowers and green leaves. The sky is a clear, light blue.

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Thursday, 15th of May

Safety-II-in-Practice 2025

Day 1

Safety-II-in-Practice 2025

Session 1

Session chair: James Norman | Independent Researcher and Airline Pilot

AI/ML FOR EXPLORING FUTURE VARIABILITY SCENARIOS IN COMPLEX SOCIOTECHNICAL SYSTEMS UNDER SAFETY-II PRINCIPLES

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Keywords: work-as-done (WAD); adaptative monitoring; performance variability; predictive modeling.

Introduction: In complex sociotechnical systems, the persistence of a gap between Work-as-Imagined (WAI) and Work-as-Done (WAD) is a recognized source of vulnerability [1], [2], [3]. While Safety-I approaches focus on analyzing failures after they occur, the Safety-II perspective emphasizes the need to understand and manage performance variability before it compromises safety [4]. A central challenge remains how to anticipate and act upon potential future deviations driven by both internal (e.g., organizational changes) and external (e.g., regulatory, environmental) dynamics. Traditionally, this anticipation relies heavily on expert judgment and experience – valuable but often limited in scalability and even on responsiveness [4], [5]. This research explores how Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) methods, especially forecasting techniques, anomaly detection, and probabilistic modeling, can be leveraged to identify early signals of variability in operational contexts. These techniques allow organizations to process extensive datasets and detect emerging patterns that may indicate future WAD scenarios, thus reinforcing resilience and decision-making. While expert judgment remains critical, we hypothesize that AI/ML can serve as a complementary analytical layer to improve foresight in line with Safety-II principles.

Methods: The methodological foundation of this study is a structured review of the literature on AI/ML applications for detecting and forecasting variability in complex systems. The focus is threefold: (a) time-series forecasting models capable of detecting performance shifts over time [6], (b) anomaly detection algorithms that highlight rare or unexpected operational behaviors [7], and (c) probabilistic models, such as Bayesian networks, that support reasoning under uncertainty and scenario-based inference [8], [9], [10]. These methods are being analyzed both from a technical

perspective and in terms of their suitability for integration into socio-technical systems that demand resilience and adaptability. In parallel, we are designing illustrative case-based examples to demonstrate how selected models can be applied in practice.

Results and Discussion: As the study is ongoing, the results presented are preliminary and intended to guide future stages of development and validation. Initial findings from the literature review suggest that AI/ML methods have strong potential to enhance the early detection of variability patterns that may not be evident through conventional monitoring approaches. For instance, time-series models [6], [11] show promise in identifying subtle trends and deviations in system behavior, while anomaly detection [7], [12] algorithms can uncover atypical signals at scale and in near real-time. Bayesian networks and other probabilistic frameworks allow analysts to model causal relations and explore potential future scenarios under different conditions [8], [10]. These capabilities are particularly relevant for addressing both endogenous variability (e.g., process drift, workload changes) and exogenous factors (e.g., market shocks, regulatory shifts, climate change) [13], [14], which may otherwise lead to normalization of deviance if left unchecked [15], [16]. Upcoming phases of the research will focus on applying the selected models to domain-relevant datasets and establishing protocols for collaborative validation with experts. Key concerns include data quality, the interpretability of ML outcomes, and the need to bridge the epistemic gap between algorithmic reasoning and practical knowledge [17], [18].

Conclusion: This work contributes to the field of safety and resilience engineering by investigating how AI/ML methods can be employed to predict operational variability in ways that are aligned with Safety-II principles. While still under development, the proposed approach emphasizes the proactive use of data to anticipate emerging risks and enhance adaptability in high-reliability organizations. The study also points to future opportunities for advancing the methodological integration between predictive analytics, expert knowledge, and safety-oriented practices, particularly in the design of more structured, adaptive, and context-aware safety systems.

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SAFETY AND RESILIENCE IN RESPONSIBLE, SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERING DESIGN, BELT AND BRACES

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Keywords: Safety, Safety II, Resilience, Responsibility, Engineering Design

Introduction: This paper explores the evolution of safety and resilience in responsible and sustainable engineering design, tracing the transition from traditional prevention-based approaches (Safety I) to resilience-focused strategies (Safety II). It reviews historical safety models, such as the

bow-tie diagram, Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA), and Hazard and Operability Studies (HAZOP), which aimed to minimize risks by preventing incidents.

However, as systems became more complex and variable, these traditional models proved insufficient in addressing all possible failure scenarios. The rise of resilience engineering recognizes that some failures are inevitable, emphasizing the need for systems to adapt and recover from disruptions.

Methods: This paper discusses the role of internal and external resilience in managing risks, highlighting both the potential benefits and challenges of relying on human ingenuity and external support systems. Case studies, including the Flixborough disaster and Boeing 737 MAX incidents, underscore the critical need to balance prevention with resilience. Ultimately, the paper advocates for an integrated approach, combining sound engineering principles with adaptive resilience strategies to ensure the safety and sustainability of modern industrial system

Conclusion: The key to responsible and sustainable engineering lies in integrating the best aspects of both Safety I and Safety II. Prevention remains essential, as it minimizes the likelihood of failures and ensures systems are robust. However, building resilience into systems allows for the flexibility needed to respond to unforeseen events. This balance ensures that while systems may not be immune to failure, they are better equipped to withstand and recover from disruptions, safeguarding both human lives and the environment. In the end, the aim of modern engineering design must be to create systems that are not only resilient but also grounded in sound engineering principles. This will require ongoing evaluation, the inclusion of adaptive measures, and a continuous reassessment of both internal and external resilience mechanisms. The increasingly popular inclusion of AI systems in designs makes this crucially important moving forward. Only by combining prevention with adaptability can engineering design achieve its ultimate goal: ensuring the safety and sustainability of industrial systems in an ever-changing world.

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INVESTIGATING FLIGHT INFORMATION SERVICE WORK-AS-DONE FOR AI-BASED SERVICE DESIGN

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Keywords: Safety-II, work-as-done, resilience, flight information service, artificial intelligence

Introduction: AI is expected to play an increasingly prominent role in making aviation more efficient and optimise performance. From a Safety-II perspective, the work-as-done (WaD) of current operations needs to be understood in terms of how it aims to meet varying demands, goals and pressures it aims to meet, in order to inform the design of AI systems for joint human-AI activity. This study investigates what characterizes Flight Information Service (FIS) WaD as a case study, why it works well currently, and how this knowledge of everyday successful FIS may be transferred to an envisioned AI tool for FIS.

Methods: The idea of AI-FIS is that pilots in uncontrolled airspace obtain flight information from an AI-based service, instead of, as currently, an air traffic controller (ATCO). Questionnaires asked pilots (6) and ATCOs (30) what well-performed Flight Information Service means, and what AI-enabled FIS would need to encompass. In addition, a focus group was held using the same questions, with three experienced ATCOs with private pilot experience. Both methods thus used a very light-weight version of resilient performance assessment [e.g., 1] on an early prototype description of the AI-FIS application.

Results and Discussion: Data analysis using thematic coding resulted in eight themes, describing characteristics of good Flight Information Service and their transfer to future AI-FIS: 1) Adapting to context; 2) Strategies of work; 3) Understanding user needs; 4) Uncertainty management; 5) Communication /coordination; 6) System interactions; 7) Cognitive work; and 8) Information management. Good Flight Information Service is highly dependent on adapting to new circumstances and sudden changes in, e.g., airspace allocation, weather conditions, and traffic. ATCO goals to always provide the highest level of service, proactively and timely, are balanced with other demands.

Conclusion: Work-as-done characteristics of current Flight Information Service have been investigated, which put a demanding set of requirements on future AI-based FIS. The study indicates that its light method is suitable for surfacing resilient performance-related aspects of envisioned AI-based operations.

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ORGANISATIONAL SELF LEARNING AT THE WORKPLACE! – A TEAM-BASED APPROACH

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Keywords: Teams, Learning, Continuous Improvement, Surprises

Introduction: RPET (Hollnagel (1)) was designed to assist and encourage work teams to “huddle” regularly to review the day’s outcomes. As well as encouraging the bonding this facilitates, it “allowed” the informal reinforcement of the vital interpersonal and unconscious cues we need to relax with, and have confidence in, our colleagues -the coffee machine / water cooler moments missing from more formal meetings. It is designed to highlight the experiences and perhaps the unnoticed, or unremarked events that allowed the work to progress successfully (as normal?), or the little surprises that heralded unexpected challenges.

It has proved very successful in healthcare situations (Denmark, Sweden, Qatar and Australia for example) and probably worth considering in most organisations, as bottom up, voluntary additions, (or substitutes?), for the now very popular top-down mandatory “Safety Moments” or “Toolbox Talks”.

The tool was developed to encourage sharing locally, but also to build a searchable record of the deliberations, recommendations, and documentation of such surprises; whether practical “quality circle” type improvements (fractional advantages?) in quality, or safety of outcomes, or instances where unexpected developments could have been a problem.

Methods: Empirisys (2), a team of engineers, process safety experts, was founded to uncover vital intelligence within organisations. This hidden data is refined into unique insights and then transformed into practical solutions. Its team of data scientists uncover its hidden value, using their proprietary software, BOOST (3), an AI-enhanced tool for categorising this data and identifying meaningful trends, which can be complex, but are real opportunities to systematically improve safety.

But having such a database is ideally what formal safety observation (near miss?) reporting systems are supposed to elicit. It seems logical to encourage and enable the development of the RPET approach, to produce a continuously updated database, which can be mined anonymously to produce a more effective monitoring facility, which in turn, can enable a more timely response and an effective way of systematically learning the impact and importance of these surprises.

The tool is being developed under the acronym,

HUDDLE

(to Highlight Unexpected events and Disseminate the Dividends Locally and Enterprise wide.)

A key innovation in HUDDLE is its integration of AI, as an advanced natural language processing (NLP) technique to analyze both formal and informal reports. Whether emerging from routine team debriefs or volunteered shared messages, the rich, unstructured data is automatically processed to extract meaningful insights. NLP helps identify recurring themes, sentiment shifts, and even subtle nuances in the language that might indicate underlying issues or innovative workarounds. By doing

so, it transforms everyday conversations and ad hoc reports into actionable data that can be cross-referenced with formal incident reports, creating a comprehensive view of organizational performance and safety.

What is being developed is a tool for monitoring (informally!) and augmenting a bottom up, local sociotechnical team sharing facility, with a top-down organisation learning and responding system; which is what standard near miss reporting systems are designed and supposed to deliver.

Results and Discussion: The process is straightforward. Teams “huddle” regularly, discussing and documenting both the challenges and the successes encountered during their work. These informal sessions, akin to the natural, spontaneous conversations that occur around a coffee machine or water cooler, are texted and digitally recorded and anonymized, transforming individual insights into a searchable, enterprise-wide database. This evolving repository is then continuously mined—using deep learning and NLP techniques—to identify patterns, extract meaningful insights, and monitor the impact of these incidents. Over time, the data reveals trends, uncovers systemic issues, and even points to innovative workarounds that can be scaled across the organization.

Figure 1 – HUDDLE’s system outline

Conclusion: Finally, what is being developed is a tool for monitoring (informally!) and augmenting a bottom-up, local sociotechnical team sharing facility, with a top-down organisation learning and responding system, which is what standard near miss reporting systems are designed and supposed to deliver.

HUDDLE will thus be a fully integrated, digitised development of RPET, which would in turn, solve the problems industry is having with the reporting, analysing and responding to, unusual event and near miss incidents. Currently they are required to do this to comply with their mandatory safety management systems. Most current systems are paper based, check list style, form filling, exercises; in which often it is merely the number of reports filed that is the statistic they are audited against.

Such systems then often require a minimum number of reports to be filed per month, which inevitably results in meaningless inventions and destroys the credibility of the system and lowers morale. This simple to implement initiative would enable and encourage (rather than dictate), the sharing of experiences and safety thinking and the lessons learned from business performance globally, in managing risk.

This can also enable some kind of recognition and reward mechanism could also be considered, but it should not be allowed to inhibit the spontaneity, or motivational empowerment benefits available from sensitive team initiative implementation

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Safety-II-in-Practice 2025

Session 2

Session chair: Natalie van der Wal | TU Delft

ENHANCING SAFETY-II THROUGH UNFORESEEN SITUATIONS IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT EXERCISES

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Keywords: crisis simulation, unexpectedness, simulation design, Safety-II

Introduction: Crisis exercises are widely regarded as a valuable tool for strengthening resilience at various levels. However, the literature highlights several limitations. Based on extensive observations of crisis exercises in the public sector Castagnino and Fayeton [1] conclude that exercises “are neither a space for experimenting with new strategies nor a simulation aimed at identifying new risks”.

To elucidate this, they argue that crisis exercises should be understood through three interrelated “spaces”, drawing an analogy with theatre. *On stage*, crisis exercises always succeed, and they never truly put result in the participants’ failure. *Behind the scenes* takes place the arduous and complex process of scenario writing in which the numerous participating organisations i) ensure participants are not placed in real difficulty (i.e. by standardised scenario writing), ii) implement what is assumed to be the optimal crisis management strategy from the outset, and iii) reinforce existing work habits and rules. *For the audience*, crisis exercises serve a reassurance function, both for the public/citizens/authorities (as a demonstration of the state’s protective role) and for participants (who, as spectators of their own individual and collective activity can reassure themselves that they are prepared to handle a crisis). This is confirmed by other studies, for example, in the nuclear sector [2], as well as in interdisciplinary emergency contexts [3], which, without using the theatrical metaphor, have reached similar results.

Another limitation of exercises is that they often take on a standardising, prescriptive or evaluative role, emphasising adherence to rules while treating deviations from protocols as mistakes. This greatly diminishes participants’ willingness and capacity to innovate – an ability that may be crucial in crises [4].

Taking stock of this, a defining feature of what we term ‘normal exercises’ is their emphasis on integrating norms, tools and procedures to prepare for crises. They typically draw on sedimented

institutional resources, i.e. what organisations are already familiar with and trained to manage, thereby reinforcing compliance with established protocols. This reflects a strong focus on Safety I. While such exercises help participants getting acquainted with these resources, some situations exceed predefined operational limits, demanding inventiveness and adaptability (e.g. the Fukushima Daiichi accident). This is where resilient performance, or Safety II becomes crucial. We define resilience as an organisation's ability to function effectively under a variety of conditions and respond appropriately to both disruptions and opportunities. In this view, resilience is not an inherent attribute of an organisation but a potential that materialises when unexpected or unpredicted changes arise [5]. However, this potential must be cultivated, raising the question of whether 'normal exercises' genuinely foster resilience as they do not offer real opportunities for it to be exercised.

However, despite the low degree of freedom in the design of normal exercises, participants may encounter situations that are not planned for in the scenario, reintroducing elements of complexity or loss of meaning [2]. We decided to empirically investigate these deviations from the scenarios to understand the way participants engage with them and how they offer expansive learning opportunities.

The study was conducted within a French national expertise institution in the nuclear field. This organisation can mobilise a stand-by team of experts within an hour of a nuclear accident alert on the French territory. The objective of the crisis team is not to directly 'manage' the crisis itself, as this the nuclear power plant operator's responsibility, but rather to provide support and recommendations regarding population protection to authorities by assessing the conditions of the affected plant (diagnosis) and forecasting the situation (prognosis).

Methods: Through direct observation, video analysis and self-confrontations [6] we analysed participants' practice and lived experience during unforeseen situations that deviated from typical exercises and were not anticipated by scenario writers. We present a case-study that was selected from a total of 90 hours of observation.

The case represents an exercise of about 7 hours, and it exhibits, due to a problem with the numerical simulator, a rare configuration for the risk of a phenomenon called a steam explosion. The *probabilistic* risk of this event is extremely hard to handle for authorities, who are used to work with *deterministic* data. The use of probabilistic data had until that day never occurred in an exercise and it was introduced for the first time, thanks to three participants who decide to engage constructively with this situation. These participants were:

- A *containment expert* who calculates the potential radiological release into the environment and determining its magnitude.
- A *crisis unit leader* who oversees the crisis unit, allocates tasks, and serves as a liaison with the Leadership Unit.
- An *evaluator of the exercise* who assesses the team's performance and leads the debriefing sessions. He also ensures the organisation's capitalisation on exercises by identifying lessons learned and directing technical issues or malfunctions to the appropriate departments.

Results and Discussion: Our results show how these three participants engaged collectively with this unforeseen event because they saw all the potential to introduce a new type of data into the exercise. They were driven by different concerns:

- The containment expert saw the rare configuration for the risk of a steam explosion in the exercise as an opportunity to address a lingering preoccupation. He has long felt uncomfortable regarding the arrival of this type of events in exercises or real crisis situations.

- The crisis unit leader saw the exercise as an opportunity to test the crisis response chain in unusual circumstances.
- The evaluator considered the rare configuration of this exercise as an opportunity to help advance the competencies of crisis team members by engaging in discussions and challenging them.

These different ways of engaging with an unforeseen situation thanks to a problem with the numerical simulator pushed these participants to act in different ways, all contributing as such to the exploitation of this situation.

- The containment expert addressed a problem that had been on his mind for over a year, working on it collaboratively with a specialised colleague, making this non-operational data applicable for crisis management and contributing to a shift in how such data is used in crisis management.
- The crisis unit leader decided to push the data produced by his colleagues to the Leadership Unit, who transferred these data to the other participating organisations in the exercise: the safety authority and local authorities.
- The evaluator accompanies the two team members to introduce a novelty in the crisis management response and to identify any further steps to safeguarding the training of other containment experts, thereby contributing to the expansion of the organisation's repertoire.

Our results illustrate how nuclear experts, during a crisis management exercise, engaged with an unforeseen situation caused by a technical issue with the simulator. Rather than merely disrupting the exercise, this unexpected event created opportunities for addressing role-related concerns, ultimately helping participants move beyond the limitations of what we term 'normal exercises'. This case study highlights how engagement with unforeseen situations fosters resilience at multiple levels:

- Individual level: Expanding repertoire by adapting to novel circumstances.
- Sociotechnical level: Integrating new types of data into the crisis response system.
- Organisational level: Advancing training methods and improving crisis management strategies.

From a Safety-II perspective, which emphasises learning from everyday work and variability rather than solely preventing failure, our findings suggest that exercises should do more than just validate procedures. They should actively create space for professionals to surface and address role-related concerns. Our results show that participants, when confronted with real-time disruptions, identify critical organisational vulnerabilities, question the completeness and applicability of existing procedures, and assess the organisation's actual readiness for events they perceive as highly probable. Rather than merely rehearsing predefined responses or reinforce compliance with them, crisis exercises should i) serve as platforms for adaptive capacity-building, ensuring that organisations can flexibly respond to unexpected challenges, and ii) offer participants a form of agency in support of organisational resilience. This demands exercises that are designed differently to enhance Safety II.

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TRANSFORMING TACIT KNOWLEDGE INTO ANTICIPATORY THINKING: A STRUCTURED APPROACH TO ENHANCING WORKER SAFETY AND PREPARING HEALTHCARE SYSTEMS FOR FUTURE CHALLENGES

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Keywords: Anticipatory Thinking, Daily Work Operations

Motivation: This abstract introduces a framework for integrating the Structured Exploration of Complex Adaptations and Anticipatory Thinking in healthcare. Through a structured method, it is

possible to capture knowledge about the daily adaptations of operational contexts. We present the first part of a PhD research project that aims to connect the knowledge of daily operations with a method to anticipate future scenarios and design improvement actions for safety.

Introduction: Uncertainty about future performance is a common challenge, especially in complex contexts like healthcare [1]. While safety in healthcare includes both patient and worker safety, the latter often receives less attention. Managing uncertainty in worker safety is increasingly important due to rising psychosocial risks such as stress, burnout, and workplace violence [2].

The Safety-I paradigm addresses future uncertainty by analyzing accidents, incidents, and near misses, and eliminating the risky conditions that caused them. The logic behind this approach is that removing hazardous conditions prevents recurrence [3].

This creates a paradox: critical events help risk managers improve safety, but reducing these events limits learning, hindering further system improvement and adaptation. Weick’s [4] concept of safety as a “dynamic non-event” suggests that the absence of accidents does not mean the system is safe. Daily “non-events”—situations where failure could have happened but didn’t—reflect normal system functioning, which is constantly evolving. From a Safety-II perspective, recognizing these non-events helps proactively prepare for future events before they occur. Non-events offer more learning opportunities than accidents, as they happen far more frequently, revealing how the system adapts to challenges.

Learning from daily context, rather than past events, helps prepare for the future by capturing weak signals—tradeoffs, adaptations, and responses that reveal the system’s direction [3].

The Structured Exploration of Complex Adaptations (SECA) Method identifies informative patterns (weak signals) of a system’s functioning based on tacit knowledge [5]. Tacit knowledge refers to the implicit understanding of how work is done in practice. This knowledge resides in individuals’ experiences, intuitions, and practical skills, acquired through direct experience and social interaction rather than formal learning. Tacit knowledge can be codified and made explicit through verbalization, when individuals become aware of adjustments and trade-offs. This explicit knowledge can then be combined with other explicit knowledge, leading to more complex and informative knowledge. This process is known as the SECI cycle, which represents the transformation of tacit to explicit knowledge and its internalization [6]. The SECA method then subsequently facilitates a qualitative approach to data collection and analysis of such a transformation of tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge. Both processes are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The SECI cycle [6] as integrated in the SECA method [5]

SECA enables understanding of tacit and implicit knowledge related to the daily adaptations of people in work systems. Since these adaptations are inherent in a system, a risk manager should have the

requisite imagination to anticipate key future possibilities. In a variable system, the ability to envision different future states ensures the system's requisite variety - the capacity to provide multiple responses to the diverse situations it may encounter [7].

Requisite imagination is linked to Anticipatory Thinking (AT), the ability to envision multiple futures based on current data [8]. AT improves the capacity to foresee events and understand consequences.

Imagination of future scenarios is based on present knowledge and past experience, so it should focus on how a system actually works, not on how it is imagined to work [9]. The SECA method helps turn implicit knowledge into wisdom for the future, but it only provides a snapshot of the system's current functioning, without offering a structured approach to proactive actions.

This abstract proposes a method to transform SECA knowledge into wisdom, using AT for possible future scenarios.

Proposed Method for planned research: The research is organized into two phases. The first identifies patterns through SECA in operational units of two Italian hospitals. The second develops a method to turn SECA results into future scenarios, aiding system improvements. A summary is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The research structure into two phases (SECA + Anticipatory Thinking [AT])

This abstract introduces the possibility of using SECA to collect data from frontline workers on daily safety-related events that go unreported but are significant for safe work. Semi-structured interviews will explore responses (personal, procedural, routine), pressures (management, external, colleagues), and conflicts (objectives, trade-offs). These isolated data don't yet reveal full system functioning. Using Grounded Theory, data can be analyzed into patterns [5].

The proposed framework in this abstract also considers a second phase which will involve transforming the SECA results into potential future scenarios using AT. The goal of this phase is to develop a method that helps support and improve the management of trade-offs and goal conflicts in operational contexts. To achieve this goal, we will present the Future Scenario Exploration and Anticipatory Thinking (FSEAT) Method, inspired by the Scenario Explorer by Argenta and colleagues [10].

The FSEAT method applies backcasting to shape future scenarios by identifying present actions [11]. It integrates explicit and tacit knowledge, compares futures, and provides a temporal framework. The process involves two groups of participants in two different stages:

- Frontline operators, who co-construct future scenarios and reflect on necessary systemic conditions (stage 1);

- Managers, who examine the organizational conditions needed to support those frontline visions (stage 2).

FSEAT is based on different steps for the two stages.

First stage: frontline operators

- Step 1. Pattern recognition

Participants are presented with the SECA results. Through group discussion, they are asked to reflect on whether they recognize themselves in the identified patterns. This phase activates the recognition mechanism in anticipatory thinking, where personal experiences are confronted with collective patterns, allowing for frame validation, challenge, or expansion.

- Step 2. Generation of ideal scenarios

Participants are asked to reflect on what would help them better manage these trade-offs, pressures, and goal conflicts in the future. The aim is to generate multiple positive scenarios.

Step 3. Backcasting from the ideal scenario

Participants select one desirable future scenario. They are asked to identify what would need to change at different levels (unit, organization, policy) to make that scenario achievable. This defines the enabling conditions for effective decision-making.

Here, participants identify conditions at:

- Micro level: the local/team level (tools, schedules, immediate leadership, training, etc.)
- Meso level: the organizational level (departmental coordination, HR policies, management systems, safety strategies, etc.)
- Macro level: the broader systemic level (sectoral policies, regulatory context, funding, industry-wide norms)

Second stage: risk managers

A similar process is repeated with managers, in two steps (no scenario generation, only reflection on the conditions needed to support the desirable future identified by operators). Managers are expected to contribute especially at meso and macro levels, where they have greater visibility and influence.

- Step 1. Pattern and scenario recognition

Managers are shown both SECA results and the ideal scenarios generated by frontline workers. They reflect on these insights, updating their own assumptions and understanding of the operational context.

- Step 2. Backcasting from the ideal scenario

Managers identify additional enabling conditions that would need to be present at micro, meso, and macro levels, for the desired scenarios to become reality. Thereby managers construct multiple scenarios, avoiding reliance on a single vision, and analyze interrelations across macro-, meso-, and the micro-level to understand their influence as represented in Figure 3. The interrelationships between the scenarios to see how they influence each other are explored.

Figure 3. The imagination of future interrelated scenarios on the three levels

Results and Discussion: The presentation based on this abstract will discuss preliminary results collected from various operating units in Italian hospitals with the SECA method. The presentation aims to explore the possibility of transforming SECA results into AT. This study is part of a PhD project, and one of the goals of this presentation is to gather feedback from the audience to refine the approach and identify potential challenges and opportunities.

Conclusion: This abstract adds another piece to the construction of knowledge through SECA, not limited to exploring the present but enabling the promotion of the required imagination necessary for the system's required variety in order to use knowledge of daily work to prepare for the future.

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REDUCING UNSTABILISED APPROACHES THROUGH LEARNING FROM STABILISED APPROACHES IN COMMERCIAL AIR TRANSPORT

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Keywords: Unstable approaches, stabilized approaches, safety-II, aviation safety

Introduction: Although the airline industry is considered ultra-safe [1], accidents still occur—some featuring numerous fatalities—yearly. According to a Flight Safety Foundation study, 65% of all airline accidents occur during approach and landing, “and 54% of all accidents could potentially be prevented by going around” [2]. I.e. by aborting an approach to landing when the aeroplane is, for instance, not flying at the right speed or vertical angle towards the runway (a so-called unstable approach) and climbing back to a safe altitude to circle around for a new approach. Airlines and aircraft manufacturers set ‘stabilised approach criteria’, parameters that flight crews must adhere to for their approach to be considered stabilised (safe) to continue to a landing. Once a flight departs these criteria, aborting the landing is compulsory. Nevertheless, empirical data from the LOSA initiative and Airbus [4], and a survey of the French Direction Générale de l’Aviation Civile [5] indicate that between 3% and 4% of all approaches are unstable and only between 1.4% and 3% of those unstable approaches are aborted by going around.

Transavia’s performance was on par with this industry standard. Since the introduction of Flight Data Monitoring (FDM)¹ in Transavia in the late 2000s, several attempts have been made to improve the number of stabilised approaches with limited success. For example, the collective performance of the pilot community in flying unstabilised approaches was relayed back to them on a structural basis, and individual cases were (and still are) selected for review with the involved flight crew in collaboration with the pilots’ union in a strictly non-punitive manner. Nevertheless, despite the company’s desire to further reduce the number of unstabilised approaches, the reduction stagnated in 2019. After the COVID-19 pandemic hit and flight operations were severely limited, a new attempt was made to improve the performance using the Safety-II school of thought. (The attempts up to that point can be described as classical Safety-I-oriented approaches aimed at reducing performance variability through procedural compliance and better understanding the ‘unstable’ approaches, i.e. “the things that go wrong” [3].)

Methods: A working group began by reviewing industry reports and FDM data to develop a new approach to improve the company’s stabilised approach performance. The main dataset was a representative sample of 5.000 flights from the company’s 50.000 total flights performed in 2019. Instead of solely analysing the unstabilised approaches, the analysis focused on why the stabilised

¹ Flight Data Monitoring is a process whereby close-to-all flights performed by an airline are evaluated using recorded flight data, usually by a dedicated department, for safety improvement.

approaches—over 95% of all approaches—were stabilised and how they differed from the unstabilised approaches. After the data analysis, adjustments were made to the approach procedures and the stabilised approach criteria and the results were monitored.

Results and Discussion: For the analysis, the definition of a stabilised approach was simplified to three criteria: being in the right aeroplane configuration (chiefly: landing gear down, flaps in landing position), being on the right vertical angle towards the runway (not too high or low), and being at the right speed (not too fast or slow). In Transavia, these criteria had to be met when the aeroplane descended through 1.000 feet of height during the approach (i.e. the stable height).

The initial analysis of the dataset revealed that over 80% of unstable approaches were unstable because of excessive speed, i.e. those flights were in the right configuration and on the right vertical angle towards the runway but flying at least 11 knots above the target speed for multiple seconds. Nearly all of the remaining unstable approaches were unstable because they were flying at too great a vertical angle towards the runway (i.e. too high), while their speed and configuration were correct. The latter predominantly occurred when aeroplanes were excessively high, and pilots decided first to bring the aeroplane into the full landing configuration by reducing speed while maintaining a constant altitude—further exacerbating their too-high vertical angle towards the runway—and then descending with the maximum amount of drag to regain the desired vertical angle towards the runway. Both kinds of unstable approaches share that the aeroplane has excessive energy².

Theoretically, if one begins timely in reducing speed and increasing drag, one could always be stabilised well in time; however, airspace design, traffic levels and all sorts of variable conditions require airliners to fly relatively fast until close to the runway, and sometimes they are given a last-minute shortcut by air traffic control. Factors like these often lead to an unstable approach [6].

The dataset showed that the stabilised approaches had one major common characteristic: they had extended the landing gear and the flaps to the intermediate setting of 15 degrees (the landing setting is 30 or 40 degrees) before crossing a virtual point of six nautical miles before the runway whilst being on the correct vertical angle towards the runway. This resulted in those flights having sufficient drag to decelerate to the desired speed before the stable height.

Next, simulator trials were conducted to validate these findings in varying conditions (e.g. landing weight, wind). A circle of six nautical miles was drawn around the runway threshold on the pilot's navigation display to visualise the latest point at which gear down and flaps 15 shall be selected. The trials showed that the six nautical miles circle on the pilot's navigation display functioned as a simple heuristic to help pilots tell the aeroplane's energy state sufficiently early on to enable them to increase their drag and reach the desired energy state at the six nautical miles circle. The trials further showed that when flying on the standard vertical angle towards the runway (3 degrees) and when extending the landing gear and flaps to 15 degrees at the latest six nautical miles from the runway, most approaches were stabilised when reaching 1.300 feet of height and nearly all were stabilised before reaching 1.000 feet. These tests included adverse conditions such as tailwinds, turbulence and delaying the subsequent flap extensions (from 15 to 30 or 40 degrees) to simulate disturbances such as contact with air traffic control. Additionally, Boeing's procedure to intercept the desired vertical angle towards the runway when the aeroplane was too high (i.e. the 'intercept from above' procedure) was tested in combination with the six nautical miles circle, and, here too, the heuristic of the circle showed pilots sufficiently early that they needed to follow the 'intercept from above' procedure to intercept the desired vertical angle by 1.000 feet.

² An airliner's energy is primarily reduced by reducing the engine's thrust to the minimum, which basically converts it into a glider. As the landing gear and flaps are extended, drag increases and the rate at which energy is dissipated increases correspondingly.

Subsequently, new approach procedures and stabilised approach criteria were written with the following key changes:

- Gear down and flaps 15 selection shall be selected at the latest six nautical miles from touchdown on all approaches. To visualise this point, a circle of six nautical miles shall be drawn around the runway threshold on the pilot's navigation display.
- Boeing's procedure was implemented to intercept the correct vertical angle towards the runway when approaching on a vertical angle that is too steep.
- Flight Safety Foundation's recommendation was implemented to follow the industry standard stabilised approach height of 500 feet when pilots can visually see the runway at the latest by three nautical miles from the runway because most pilots believe that an unstable approach can still safely be aborted at 500 feet [2]. The stabilised approach height remained at 1.000 feet for all other meteorological conditions.

As soon as these new procedures were trained to all pilots, the procedures were activated, and the pilot's performance in flying stabilised approaches was monitored closely. After one year, the following change was measured in the year 2021 in comparison to 2019 (2020 was not used for comparison due to the major COVID-induced disruptions in flight operations):

- The number of unstabilised approaches had decreased by 37% year-on-year to 2.65%; below the 3% to 4% range measured by the Flight Safety Foundation [4] and surveyed by the French Direction Générale de l'Aviation Civile [5].
- The number of flights with unstable approaches selected for review with the involved flight crew dropped from 34 potential flights, of which 12 were selected, to seven, year-on-year.

Conclusion: The project showed a marked improvement in stabilised approach performance, the size of the improvement exceeding the expectations of the workgroup. Whereas mitigating measures before the project targeted behavioural and attitude changes, which were based on the hypothesis that flying unstabilised approaches bore a behavioural or attitudinal source, the project showed that looking at work-as-done to learn from things that go well and then creating procedures and heuristics around those practices works. This finding calls into question the industry's understanding of pilots' behaviour and skills concerning flying stabilised approaches, which, in turn, may challenge the industry's understanding of other (safety) issues. Notwithstanding, other airlines have realised improvements through different avenues, such as Porter Airlines [7], which focused on a go-around policy that was more supported by their pilots—an approach recommended by the Flight Safety Foundation [2]—and resulted in more aborted approaches and an improvement in the amount of stabilised approaches.

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Safety-II-in-Practice 2025

Session 2

The Paradigm of Controlability and Beyond

Session leaders

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THE PARADIGM OF CONTROLLABILITY AND BEYOND

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Keywords: system performance management; ETTO; trade-offs, Control paradigms, Free-Energy

In safety-critical domains, the pursuit of “safe operations” has long been framed around the prevention of adverse events through, typically, risk management. However, such a narrow focus fails to account for the true goals of complex systems: to maintain coherent and sustained operations that continuously balance safety and productivity under conditions of uncertainty and performance variability, (e.g.) unexpected events.

Performing resiliently is a key ability that socio-technical systems should possess. The emergence of unexpected events, driven by the inherent complexity of socio-technical systems, has challenged traditional safety science over time especially. This has led to a gradual shift away from a risk-focused perspective, toward a resilience-oriented one. While the risk-based approach emphasized the need for knowledge in order to exercise control, the resilience perspective recognizes the limits of what can be known, and instead favours the system's ability to adapt in the face of surprises.

Accordingly, demonstrating adaptation requires not being prepared to what might happen, laying in a state of “ignorance”, where the unknown is – however – correctly managed. At the extreme, the system that is potentially the most capable of adapting, is the one with least knowledge. But does that make it the most resilient, too? The answer is likely no. Trade-offs are around the corner [1]. A certain level of control – and knowledge that comes with it – is indeed essential for managing the unknown, resiliently. One might therefore assume that the more a system is controlled – and the more

it knows – the better it is prepared to the unknown, thereby favouring control over adaptation to ensure the resilient performance. We have hints this is not true at all.

The RESIST Project

During the RESIST project (RESilience Management for Industrial Systems Threats – cf. the acknowledgment section), the research team (here represented by F.S. and R.P.) carried out an experimental campaign involving Human-Hardware-in-the-Loop (HHIL) simulations [2]. The HHIL approach combines real-world data from human operations and hardware functioning with a digital model of the complex system under analysis to ensure high-fidelity simulation results. The simulations involved human operators to detect failures and then restore operations on a mock-up plant mimicking an oil and gas extraction process. Different operator personas were tested, ranging from those working under tightly controlled conditions to those given greater freedom to adapt, depending on the level of practicability of the work conditions. A simple resilience measure computed over the simulations results shows how different personas performed worse (on average) and more variably at both extremes (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Exemplary results related to the observations from the HHIL simulation campaign.

While these early results are not yet statistically significant, the empirical observations suggested that controllability and adaptability cannot be pushed in isolation. Instead, the two “forces” must be balanced to place the system in a state with a greater potential for performing resiliently.

If complex adaptive socio-technical systems must be capable of functioning safely, purposefully sustaining adaptive capacity, then we must ask: what kind of system design and organisational approach makes that possible in a complex, variable world?

What are the implications for controllability and adaptability?

A truly stable system must survive in a world full of surprises. Ashby’s Law of Requisite Variety states that to remain viable, a system must be able to respond to every type of perturbation it might face. In this sense, what is referred to is adaptability or adaptive capacity.

Since the number of possible disruptions is practically infinite; no system can rely on predefined responses alone. Not all contingencies can be engineered in advance. Neither, significantly, is there unlimited or limitless adaptive capacity, The cost of coordination becomes increasingly limiting for

example. We contend that two kinds of capacity are required: (i) designed control, and (ii) emergent creativity.

In complexity terms, many desired states are “multiply realisable” – reachable through many pathways. But not all paths work every time. The ability to flex, adapt, and explore is key.

The free energy principle: A model for system coherence

Last year, we proposed the Free Energy Principle (FEP) as a framework for understanding adaptive system behaviour [3]. The FEP, originating in theoretical neuroscience [4], posits that systems maintain coherence by minimising surprise (or ‘free energy’) through learning and prediction [5]. This implies several key design principles:

- Distributed sense-making: Systems persist by dispersing learning and processing across multiple layers;
- Predictive processing: Systems function best when they can anticipate, not merely react to, their environment.

From this standpoint, centralised command-and-control is a poor fit for dynamic, real-world operations. The cognitive and informational load is too high, the pace of change too fast. Instead, distributed control and adaptive autonomy are essential.

Designing for adaptive capacity

If we apply this insight to organisational design, the implications are evident:

- We must maintain both structure that resists upset (robustness) and structures that enable adaptation (resilience);
- Learning must be both explicit (codified, documented) and implicit (tacit, emergent);
- System design must intentionally maximise the flow of information and knowledge across formal and informal networks.

Humans are naturally good at this. We are self-networking entities, capable of sharing knowledge in unexpected, generative ways – if we are given the conditions and psychological safety to do so.

Safety-I has focused heavily on accident prevention through root cause analysis and engineered control – valuable for known, repeatable risks. It helps with robustness.

Safety-II, on the other hand, encourages us to learn from what goes ‘well’ or ‘successfully’ (whatever these actually mean?) – understanding variability in performance and successful adaptations. It points toward resilience. But Safety-II has often stalled in practice. One reason may be the lack of a compelling conceptual models to ensure it can be translated into practice.

A new framework: Constraints and patterning

In complex systems, stability is not imposed – it is enacted. Patterns of behaviour emerge from the constraints imposed on actors, processes, and technologies. These constraints may be:

- Fixed (e.g., gravity, regulation);
- Enabling (e.g., the rules of a game); or
- Emergent (e.g., social norms, cultural practices).

To support resilience, we must shift from trying to optimise systems toward designing constraint architectures that enable both robustness and adaptation. This means designing for flexibility, adaptability, experimentation, and generative learning.

Looking ahead: What we must do

If we want Safety-II to become more than a marginal idea, we must:

- Redesign our organisations to allow for distributed learning, emergent intelligence, and adaptive autonomy;
- Recognise that most human knowledge is socially developed and embedded in informal practices, not just formal procedures;
- This is not a rejection of Safety-I, but an expansion. Robustness and resilience are not opposites – they are complementary. Together, they create the coherent, adaptive systems we need.

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Friday, 16th of May

Safety-II-in-Practice 2025

Day 2

Safety-II-in-Practice 2025

Session 3

Session Chair: Maria Calero Gonzalez | University of Nottingham

DARK SECRET IN SAFETY

Bart Vanraes

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Keywords: underreporting, occupational accidents, safety culture, zero accidents

Introduction: Despite decades of investment in occupational safety and a steady decline in officially reported injury rates, empirical studies consistently reveal substantial underreporting of workplace accidents and illnesses [1], [2], [3]. Sometimes, employers prefer not to deal with accidents that raise difficult questions or bring extra costs [4], [5], [6]. Employees, too, may stay silent out of fear, worried about punishment, missing out on bonuses, or losing promotion opportunities [6], [7], [8]. This phenomenon, previously termed “tippexaccidents” by the author of this abstract [9] refers to work-related incidents that are concealed, ignored, or misclassified, thereby distorting safety metrics and masking the true risk landscape. The concept of “tippexaccidents” is a form of organizational silence undermining the capacity for organizational learning and improvement. Safety-II relies on organizations learning from all safety data, from things that go wrong, things that go right, and everything in between. It includes eventdriven Safety-I data, but is also critical of not basing safety management systems on Safety-I data only. This abstract motivates why solely relying on Safety-I data for safety management is inherently limited and even distorts the actual status of a safety system. Rather than an anomaly, these practices are found to be widespread and deeply embedded across industries and organizational cultures.

Methods: This study draws on a triangulated methodology. It involved over 200 anonymous surveys among safety professionals, workers, and accident victims, personal interviews, in combination with an exploratory literature review. These were complemented by in-depth interviews and case studies, including severe underreporting cases in Belgium and abroad. In addition, dozens of peer-reviewed academic papers and government reports were reviewed to contextualize the findings within the broader field of occupational safety and underreporting. Together, these sources enabled a cross-validation of themes and patterns related to systemic underreporting, cultural drivers, and statistical blind spots.

Results and Discussion: Findings in the literature indicate that underreporting is not merely anecdotal but is structurally incentivized by financial, reputational, and regulatory pressures [10].

Employers may reclassify incidents, shift accident locations, or coerce workers into “light duty” assignments to avoid triggering reportable events, a practice exacerbated by performance regimes such as “Zero Accident” policies. These policies, can foster a culture of silence and blame, discouraging open reporting and eroding trust. Missing data skews analysis and illustrates the methodological blind spots created by these practices.

From a Safety-II perspective, underreporting constitutes a form of functional blindness: the system fails to recognize and learn from the reality of everyday work, even if this reality distorts the Safety-I event-driven data, which is the point of departure for the Safety-II understanding of normal work. Safety-II advocates for a shift from reactive, numbers-driven safety management to a proactive, learning-oriented approach that values all safety signals, including near-misses, weak signals, and informal reports, as critical inputs for continuous improvement. This requires fostering a reporting culture, characterized by psychological safety and just responses to disclosures, and redefining performance metrics to prioritize learning over compliance.

In conclusion, “tippexaccidents” expose both ethical and methodological deficiencies in traditional safety management. Addressing this dark secret demands an ethical turn: leadership must move beyond superficial metrics that cannot be trusted, actively encourage transparent reporting, and implement systems that treat every safety-related event as an opportunity for learning and improvement. If Safety-I data, such as reports of incidents, accidents, or deviations, cannot be trusted due to underreporting or selective recording, then Safety-II efforts risk building on a flawed foundation. After all, how can we understand what goes right if we have an incomplete or distorted picture of what goes wrong? Relying solely on Safety-I data to understand safety provides, at best, a partial view—one that often overlooks everyday adaptations, near-misses, and the silent work that prevents failure. To truly grasp how systems succeed under pressure, we must go beyond incident counts and embrace richer sources of insight that capture the realities of normal work, not just its breakdowns. Only by confronting what is hidden can organizations hope to achieve genuine, resilient safety.

Figure 1: A blind spot for safety management. LEFT “Damage to returning aircraft led analysts to reinforce the wrong areas — until they realized the planes that didn’t return were the real source of insight. Underreported workplace accidents create a similar blind spot.” | RIGHT, “Workplace accidents are often ‘corrected’ or erased for the sake of performance indicators. But what gets covered up cannot be learned from.”

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ADAPTING ON THE FLY: A DATA-DRIVEN APPROACH TO CAPTURE ADAPTIVE BEHAVIORS IN COLLABORATIVE HUMAN-MACHINE SYSTEMS

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Keywords: adaptive capacity, goal adaptation, graceful extensibility, neurophysiology; phygital twin; simulation; training

Introduction: One thing is for sure: if a system wants to survive over time, it must adapt to changes [1]. This has been evident for ages, in any system, whether natural or artificial ones. All agents within collaborative systems - whether the collaboration is human-to-human, human-to-machine, or a combination of both – tend to adapt to successfully achieve their common goals. From a Safety-II perspective, this capacity is decisive and requires dedicated investigations since it makes the system more effective and more resilient to disturbances[2]. This is reflected, among others, in Woods' Theory of Graceful Extensibility (TGE) [3]. But how can we recognize and – eventually – measure if and to which extent a system is capable of adapting? This research proposes a data-driven approach to capture adaptive behaviors in collaborative systems. The proposed approach relies on the analysis of communication and neurophysiological signals. In particular, agents' Electroencephalogram (EEG), Electrodermal activity (EDA) and Photoplethysmogram (PPG) are collected during the operations of a collaborative system in which multiple agents interact and perform tasks in order to achieve a common goal. To instantiate the methodological solution with a realistic use case, the approach has been applied in the context of a simulation platform designed to train non-technical skills, whose utility can be valid for various domains (e.g., aviation operators, medical staff).

Methods: The approach proposed in this research involves three key steps:

- The **identification of the system's activities, plans, and goals**. This step consists in recognizing the whole set of activities that system agents can perform, grouping of such activities into activity plans, and associating each plan to one (or a set of) system goal(s).

- The **collection of data during the execution of the system processes**. Collected data comprehends the recording of communication among agents, and their neurophysiological signals (EEG, EDA and PPG).
- The **analysis of collected data**. In this step, the communication data are linked to the system’s activities and – in turn – to plans, and goals. In parallel, the agents’ neurophysiological signals are analyzed to assess their workload levels and teamwork during the execution of the system processes. Thus, neurophysiological signals offer a measure of the coordination cost associated with the system's adaptive capacity. Both the activity-plan-goal data, and the neurophysiological ones are time-based, thus, comparable to letting the interplay among adaptive and collaborative behaviors emerge from them.

Results and Discussion: The proposed approach has been applied to a set of simulation sessions. The simulation platform employed here is usually played with air traffic controllers in the gamified context of the management of a space station. Participants are assigned roles on two “decks”, i.e., Support and Main, where they are tasked with managing the battery charging and the power generation of the spaceship, trying to travel as much distance as possible. The simulation involves coordinating the transport of batteries via a lift system, needing both decks to communicate effectively to complete the system’s missions. These latter are assigned and change over time, based on the simulation scenario. Additionally, in specific scenarios, unexpected events challenge participants to adapt in real-time. The simulation is thus customizable, with varying mission complexities. For this study, three 10-minute entry-level scenarios were used to collect data. The first step involves an ex-ante analysis of the system operations to identify activities, plans, and goals that the agents might execute during the process. This allows for the creation of a structured frame within which agent behaviors can be assessed. For the scenarios tested, 23 activities, 4 plans, and 3 goals were identified. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows an exemplary plan, its component activities, and the goal it pursues.

Table 1: Activities constituting plan P1_1, which is aimed at achieving goal G1, along with their description and the agents involved. The table includes an excerpt of all identified activities, plans, and goals.

ID Goal	Goal description	ID Plan	Plan description	ID Activity	Activity description	Agent involved
G1	Score points	P1_1	Go faster	A1_1_0_S	Communication about battery charge level sufficient to increase speed	Support
				A1_1_0_M	Communication about energy level sufficient to increase speed	Main
				A1_1_1	Communication about panel closure	Support
				A1_1_2	Communication about the increase in extra-thrust	Main
				A1_1_3	Communication about the monitoring of battery level to decide if go faster	Support/Main
...

The data collection in the second step needed the setup of equipment to record real-time communication and collect agents’ neurophysiological signals. In this research, communication is recorded using microphones capable of distinguishing the voices of the different players, while each player wears a device to record their neurophysiological signals. This setup ensures the continuous recording of both communication and neurophysiological signals during the simulations, without significantly affecting the players’ capabilities, and – consequently – the significance of collected data.

After the execution of simulations, the recorded communication is postprocessed to filter out background noise and disturbances, ensuring the data represents only relevant interactions. An automated tool is then used to extract and log all communications in a structured format, i.e., a sorted list which captures the start and end times of each interaction, as well as the content of the

conversation. These data is then manually tagged to the respective activities – and in turn –, plans, and goals, allowing for the identification of the agents' roles and the tasks they were working on at any given time. Similarly, neurophysiological data is postprocessed to ensure the removal of signal noise and have representative metrics.

Error! Reference source not found. shows two representative excerpts of the data being analyzed. It is possible to notice how in the first simulation (i.e., left-hand side, cf. **Error! Reference source not found.**), the agents typically stay on the same plan for extended periods, reflecting strong alignment and coordination in their activities, with fewer transitions between plans. In contrast, the second simulation (i.e., right-hand side, cf. **Error! Reference source not found.**) features more frequent plan changes, along with a shorter average duration for each plan.

The integration of communication and neurophysiological data helps analyzing how changes in activities, plans, or goals correlate with shifts in neurological signals, offering a more holistic view of agents' behaviors and teamwork dynamics. Specific indicators were also defined to assess the evolution of activities over time. These indicators included (e.g.) the frequency of activity shifts, and the frequency of activity shifts over the activity duration. These measures helped uncover recurring behavioral patterns, alignment or misalignment between agents over time, and the overall dynamics of the system.

Figure 1: Excerpts of plans and goals evolution during the two simulations.

Conclusion: This research introduces a novel approach for tracking and analyzing collaborative behaviors, focusing on the shifts in activities, plans, and goals within collaborative systems, along with the evaluation of neurophysiological signals. This preliminary study opens up a set of new opportunities for improving training protocols and understanding the adaptive behaviors of collaborative system agents. The identification of recurring behavioral patterns could be leveraged to improve teamwork strategies, as well as to identify weak signals that allow for the anticipation of potentially harmful events. The ultimate aim is to drive thorough analyses, potentially preventive and predictive, fostering safer and more human-centric environments where human operators can be more comfortable acting and sustaining operations successfully, even in futuristic endeavors (e.g., advanced surgeries, complex aerospace operations). Otherwise, what is the point of being at the forefront of technology?

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GENDER ANALYSIS OF THE RESILIENCE ENGINEERING SCIENTIFIC FIELD

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Keywords: Resilience Engineering, Semantic Analysis, Gendered Assessment

Introduction: Resilience Engineering (RE) has emerged over the past two decades as a novel and interdisciplinary field dedicated to understanding how complex systems can adapt and sustain operations in the face of unexpected disruptions. Originating at the intersection of systems engineering, human factors, safety science, and organizational studies, RE offers a transformative perspective on how to design, manage, and evaluate systems to be not only safe but also flexible and robust. Despite its growing influence in critical sectors such as aviation, healthcare, energy, and transportation, the internal structure of the RE research landscape remains largely unexplored.

As the field matures, it becomes increasingly important to map its discipline boundaries and to uncover the subfields and thematic clusters that have emerged over time [1]. Doing so can help us understand how resilience is conceptualized (i.e., how the term is defined and framed), operationalized (i.e., how resilience is implemented and measured in practical settings), and prioritized (i.e., the extent to which resilience is emphasized relative to other concerns such as efficiency or compliance, whether in academic research agendas, policy directives, funding allocations, or real-world implementation). This can also reveal the evolving dynamics of the community that produces this knowledge consisting of academic papers.

Concurrently, there is growing recognition of persistent gender disparities in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) disciplines. These disparities manifest not only in terms of participation and representation but also in authorship, recognition, and influence within academic communities. While several studies have examined gender gaps in established STEM fields [2][3], there remains a gap in our understanding of how these dynamics play out within emerging interdisciplinary areas such as Resilience Engineering.

This paper seeks to address this knowledge gap through a two-fold objective. First, we aim to unveil the structure of the Resilience Engineering research community by identifying and characterizing its subfields. This involves analyzing publication trends, conferences and workshops, and thematic patterns that illustrate how the field has evolved. Second, we focus on conducting a gender-based analysis of these subfields, investigating the degree of gender representation and potential disparities across different areas of RE research. In doing so, we aim to contribute both to the ongoing development of the RE domain and to broader efforts aimed at fostering equity and inclusivity within this scientific discipline.

Methods: The methodology we are using for the analysis begins with the retrieval of 945 papers related to Resilience Engineering from the Scopus repository. From these papers, the keywords are extracted both from Scopus and, automatically, by using Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, validated by humans, and tokenized into single-word elements to facilitate a more granular analysis. To mitigate the influence of overly general terms such as “resilience”, we applied an upper frequency threshold in our NLP analysis. Keywords exceeding this threshold were excluded from the final selection to ensure a more meaningful and discriminative set of terms. Using these tokens, two similarity matrices are constructed, the former based on similarity between single-word tokens and the latter based on similarity between the full set of selected keywords. These matrices serve as the foundation for clustering using the k-means and the elbow methods, where related keywords are grouped together to uncover thematic subfields within the broader domain of Resilience Engineering. To enhance interpretability, each cluster is then labeled using a large language model (LLM), which provides meaningful and coherent names for the identified subfields. To label each cluster of keywords, we provided the full list of terms within the cluster as input to the LLM. We then followed an iterative process, refining the labels with the LLM to ensure clarity and to minimize overlap between topics across different clusters. Finally, a gender analysis is conducted across these clusters to explore patterns of representation and detect any gender disparities within the various branches of the field.

Methodology for gender analysis of the resilience engineering scientific field

Results and Discussion: The analysis of keyword similarities and subsequent clustering revealed five distinct subfields within the Resilience Engineering research landscape. The clusters range from regulatory and compliance topics to human-centered resilience, cyber resilience, and resilience in high-risk environments such as aviation, healthcare, and emergency response.

Preliminary partial findings indicate a gender imbalance within the Resilience Engineering research community, with male authors significantly outnumbering female authors. While our preliminary findings indicate a general underrepresentation of female researchers within the Resilience Engineering community, we recognize that this pattern may not be uniform across all thematic areas. The structural mapping of the field provides a unique opportunity to investigate whether certain subfields, such as those focused on human-centered resilience or regulatory frameworks, demonstrate higher or lower inclusivity compared to more technical or emerging domains like cyber resilience. Although a detailed breakdown of gender representation by subfield is still underway, future work will specifically explore these variations to provide a more nuanced understanding of where disparities are most pronounced, and where progress is being made.

Conclusion: The identification of five distinct subfields within Resilience Engineering provides valuable insight into the structure and thematic diversity of this evolving scientific domain. However, the preliminary gender analysis reveals a notable imbalance, with male researchers being more prominently represented across the community. These findings highlight the need for further studies to deepen our understanding of gender dynamics within each subfield. Moreover, they underscore the importance of developing targeted initiatives and raising awareness to foster a more inclusive research environment, one that encourages and supports greater participation from underrepresented groups, particularly women, in shaping the future of Resilience Engineering. For instance, we recommend targeted measures, such as conference awards for women and gender quotas in conference committees, to boost female participation, visibility, and influence in Resilience Engineering, fostering a more balanced and inclusive field.

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